

PROJECT DELIVERABLE

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Abbreviation List

Abbreviation	Definition
BC	Blockchain
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
KOM	Kick-off meeting
TCA	Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A.

Executive Summary

A project web site has been designed, developed and operated by TCA, through a service provider identified for the scope.

The design of the TRUSTyFOOD project website is here presented. Figures incorporated among the sections of the deliverable are supplementary for the visual representation of the different website areas.

1. Website domain

A new domain has been purchased by TCA and registered (www.trustyfood.eu). The registration was performed on 06 October 2022. Regarding the hosting, it will be renewed on a yearly basis.

The website is currently officially online.

2. Website aim

The aim of the website is to reach a wide range of interested audience and target bodies. It includes all the relevant information about the project.

The website serves as a major dissemination and information channel of the project. Visitors have access to all information about the project; they can download the project's promotional material, read news & events and the public deliverables, contact the consortium etc.

3. Website responsible

Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A. (Project Coordinator) will be in charge for uploading new information/documents, while the entire consortium will contribute to generate the contents.

4. Website structure

The web has been designed by an external company (Viva Digital).

The website contains only public sections, which will be periodically updated as the project advances.

The current information is organized through a simple yet standard menu, which is indicated below:

3.3.1. Home page

The figure below (figure 1) shows the **home page** of TRUSTYFOOD web portal with the navigation bar divided into six Sections:

- About
- Partners
- News
- Documents
- Framework of Services
- Contact

Figure 1. Home Page

The first element that stands out on the left of the screen is the **project logo**.

The purpose of a logo is to give a visual representation of a brand. The logo design should be unique, give high impact, be eye-catching and leave an unforgettable impression.

In designing it, Confagricoltura (in strict collaboration with TCA) has put the attention on the following main aspects:

- Design had to be eye-catching but simple
- Design had to support the project message for some years
- Design fonts and colours had to compliment the project message

Figure 2. Project's logotype

The font and colours used are:

Font: 29LT Bukra

Colour code for chain: #B6E89E (green)

Colour code for acronym: #000000

The logo was created also in the following form: transparent, high resolution.

Without clicking on the Sections available on the navigation bar, but simply scrolling down the page with the mouse cursor, we see – in order:

- the header,
- the main messages the project intends to transfer, Our Partners, the connection with the latest News - *that make up all together the body of the page*,
- the footer.

In detail:

- Two project's mottos "Providing future scenarios and a roadmap for a wide agri-food blockchain implementation" and "TRUSTyFOOD aims to provide support to the Strategic Research Agenda of the future joint research program about Blockchain" appear in the foreground of the page, to summarize the purpose of the project. Here a green bottom is available to "discover more" about the project or take "contacts".
- Then, the page continues presenting the questions the project poses itself and the general approach:

Blockchain emerging technology: hype or a big opportunity?

Blockchain: an evolving technology

Innovation in blockchain architectures, applications and business concepts is happening at a fast pace.

Learning the real value of blockchain

The hype and the exaggeration that have surrounded the technology led to misplaced expectations and misunderstandings.

Different uses and applications

Before adopting Blockchain technologies, it's necessary to evaluate the specific context and the economy. BCTs could have different uses and shapes according to the specific purpose to which they applied.

[About TRUSTyFOOD](#)

Benefits and opportunities of Blockchain technology in the food system

Benefits and opportunities
Blockchain can contribute to the successful food system transition towards more sustainable and transparent supply chains, preserve the environment and increase societal resilience.

Farm-to-fork vision

The food chain approach
TRUSTyFOOD project aims to implement blockchain applications in the food system by enlarging the knowledge and the awareness about this technology among stakeholders.

- **Our Partners** (connection with the related Section on the navigation bar)
- **News** (connection with the related Section on the navigation bar)
- In the footer of the website, the official EU emblem has been placed following the EC communication rules:

3.3.2. About

In the navigation bar at the top right of the Home page, the first Section is represented by “About”. The section is in turn divided into submenus:

– Objectives

Main objective of the project and related intermediate ones are listed and described in this section. To complement the previous information, the project outputs are also presented

– Methodology

The set of methodologies TRUSTyFOOD intends to apply are briefly depicted

– Project structure

The four main operational Phases, around whom the whole proposal revolves, are reported in a self-explanatory scheme

Figure 3 (a, b, c and d) shows a screenshot of the information contained in the section “about”.

(a)

The screenshot shows the 'About - TRUSTyFOOD' page on the website trustyfood.eu/about/. The page features a light green background with abstract leaf patterns. It contains five main objective icons with corresponding text:

- Enlarge the knowledge base and insight into Blockchain applications in different domains and in the food system, both through primarily public data sources as well as activating a stable dialogue with stakeholders** (Icon: Network of nodes)
- Identify drivers and barriers (e.g. why communities, i.e. users, accept/reject blockchain-based projects, the mistakes done by others for not repeating them, the best and innovative practices in blockchain development in agri-food sector – considering its complexity)** (Icon: Magnifying glass over a graph)
- Arrive to formulate recommendations (both to public authorities and private stakeholders) on how blockchain technologies can contribute to the successful food system transition towards more sustainable and transparent supply chains, preserve the environment and increase societal resilience** (Icon: Power button)
- Provide future scenarios and a roadmap for agri-food blockchain implementation** (Icon: Double-headed arrow)
- Set up of an innovative framework of services for prompt, easy and effective application of BC-technology in the agri-food sector** (Icon: Gear)

Below these objectives, a paragraph states: "The project will investigate and discuss both technical aspects through the involvement of experts as well as non-technical barriers to BCTs deployment, the main focus being on its acceptance from farmers and all the other supply chain players, mitigation of the environmental impact and ensuring finance for adoption. Other issues fostering BCTs deployment will be considered, such as interoperability, innovative business models, standardisation and regulatory issues."

Project outputs:

- R&I Roadmap for blockchain technologies in the agri-food sector, as a portfolio of R&I priorities and activities, to prepare the way for R&I activities for the decade to come,
- A series of White Papers addressed to EC and Governments but also to researchers and innovators,
- A framework of services (and guidelines) addressed to practitioners and users for empowering them in future BC technology implementation

(b)

The screenshot shows the 'Methodology' page on the website trustyfood.eu/about/. The page has a white background with a central image of fresh produce (lemons, corn, tomatoes) arranged around a circular diagram of blue cubes connected by dots. The text on the page is as follows:

Methodology

TRUSTyFOOD intends to apply the following set of methodologies:

- **Mapping and analysing, making clearness on the state-of-the-art**
We need for a larger number of real-world case studies to evaluate the best approach for the use of BCT to food supply chain. The diversity within this wide pallet of innovative activities will have to be taken into account to identify the flexibility required by food system's different contexts. The growing number of applications makes it possible to study and understand different facets of the technology and enables realistic assessment of the potentials and challenges.
- **Dialogue with stakeholders for co-creation and consensus building**
Co-creation signals the design of various stakeholders in the design of a technological project or development trajectory. The added value of this model includes: (1) the communication and collaboration among all involved disciplines, thus multidisciplinary; (2) an inclusive player-centric approach geared to reframes insights and contribute to actual transformation, thus transdisciplinary. This signals that the most robust and sustainable solutions will come from designing with (and not just for) end-users. To this end, a participatory approach will be applied that builds on two main components: the consultation of stakeholders with the aim to identify the current state of the art of BC experimentation and the co-creation of a participatory vision and scenarios for future applications in the context of future R&I strategic policies.

(c)

(d)

Figure 3. About TRUSTyFOOD project

3.3.3. Partners

The section “PARTNERS” hosts the information of each partner of TRUSTyFOOD project (Figure 4). For each organisation, it is included the logo of the organisation and the name.

Partners

Beneficiaries and affiliated entities represent 7 EU countries (Croatia, Germany, Greece, Italy, Luxembourg, The Netherlands and Portugal) and 1 third country (Egypt).

<p>Tecnoalimenti S.C.p.A. https://www.tecnoali.com/home-en/</p>	
<p>Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis https://www.certh.gr/root.en.aspx</p>	 <small>Institutes Involved</small>
<p>Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V. https://www.fraunhofer.de/en.html</p>	
<p>University of Koblenz-Landau https://www.uni-koblenz-landau.de/en</p>	
<p>Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores Inovação https://www.inov.pt/en/index.html</p>	
<p>INESC-ID https://www.inesc-id.pt/</p>	
<p>Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A. https://www.eng.it/en/</p>	
<p>Stichting VU https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/research-institutes/athena-institute</p>	
<p>Udruga za razvoj suradnje na unaprjeđenju tehnologije u prehrambenom sektoru https://agrifoodcroatia.com/</p>	
<p>Confagricoltura https://www.confagricoltura.it/eng/</p>	
<p>North South Consultants Exchange LLC https://nsce-inter.com/</p>	
<p>Compellio SA https://compellio/</p>	
<p>World Farmer Organisation https://www.wfo-oma.org/</p>	

Figure 4. Partners: partners name, logo and website

3.3.4. News

This section will cover news and events related to the project and will be updated often with new information in order to keep the audience aware of the project progress as well as about potential events or news that could be interesting due to its relation with project topic. Currently, information on KOM and first public presentations are included.

Figure 5. News

3.3.5. Documents

This section will gather all the material available to the user. In order to have the information categorised so the user can find and download the material easily, two subsections have been included (figure 6):

- Communication material** - documents/sheets considered to be helpful to promote the project are available here. Particularly, project leaflet (brochure), roll-up, Fact sheets and all the documents aimed to construct the corporative image of the project will be gathered under this subsection;
- Deliverables** - In order to increase the dissemination impact of the results to be generated and for sharing the knowledge (in line with the Data Management Plan), the public deliverables will be published under this section and the download option will be set up for free. Since M8, with the first results generated in relation to the mapping and collection activity, more contents will be added.

In the future, additional items will be added to the submenu (e.g. Roadmap, White Papers, Policy Brief, Publications).

Figure 6. Documents

3.3.6. Framework of Services

Such field is currently inactive, since the Framework of Service will be finalized later on along the project lifespan. Even if operated by Engineering Ingegneria Informatica, it will be described inside the TRUSTyFOOD website. The framework of services described will be an easy to use toolbox able to facilitate the understanding of the technology potential and limits and giving practical examples in specific contexts.

The idea is to create an environment where potential users can:

- easily evaluate if the technological characteristics are suitable to their context and needs
- Be facilitated in defining the specific application that better suit to their own specificities
- Be facilitated in the uptake of the BC technologies exploiting its potential

The framework of services will have the shape of a guideline aiming to support specific stakeholders such as (small) farmers and other food supply chain players for use-cases application and assessment.

3.3.7. Contact

The “CONTACT” section (Figure 7) includes the references to the project coordinator and the project’s email.

In addition, a simple form where basic information is required is included. The data inserted in the form will arrive as an email to the project coordinator. This page will allow stakeholders to ask for more information directly to the project partners, in order to create a networking possibility with other projects and initiatives.

A contact form titled 'Get in touch' with the subtitle 'Contact TRUSTyFOOD'. The form contains six input fields: 'Name', 'Surname', 'Email', 'Phone', 'City', and 'Address'. A green 'Send Request' button is positioned at the bottom right of the form area.

Figure 7. Contact

5. Other topics

Aspects related to *legal notice*, *cookies policy*, *privacy policy* are managed.

The website has been studied to be compatible with Mobile visualisation.

Link to project's Social Media are available both through the navigation bar, in CONTACT Section and in the footer.

Project Coordinator

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Social

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